

ADVANTAGES AND CONVENIENCES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TODAY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13843587>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-sentabr 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 21-sentabr 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 26-sentabr 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

Foreign language, cognitive and analytical ability, modern method, speech patterns, free communication

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the demand for learning foreign languages by many people today and the benefits, advantages and convenience of learning foreign languages. The effectiveness of teaching a foreign language depends on the degree of students' interest in learning it.

In today's developing era, knowledge of foreign languages is becoming a demand of the times. In order to become a mature and perfect master of his profession, every person should know and learn one or two foreign languages in addition to his own language. And this process helps us to rise further. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "A child who learns a profession and a language from school is a great achievement of our society, the one who does not know it is a problem" [1].

Nowadays, as our country is developing, the demand for foreign languages is increasing. As a result, many young people are learning foreign languages with their own interest and passion. Also, effective work is being done to introduce foreign languages to children from kindergarten age and to teach these languages in different ways and methods. That is, a child has some knowledge of a foreign language before school age, and later he can easily learn this language more deeply from school. The most important thing is that learning foreign languages today gives us great opportunities. That is, if you know a foreign language, you will have the opportunity to meet new people, make new friends, colleagues, and freely communicate with foreigners. Another advantage of learning foreign language is that knowing a foreign language will greatly help improve your cognitive and analytical skills. If you learn a foreign language every day and develop it day by day, that is, if you memorize words and perform various exercises every day, your cognitive and analytical skills will increase [2]. A good way to increase your knowledge and social circle while learning a language is to connect and talk with people who are learning the language. Nowadays, more and more employers are looking for people who are fluent in foreign languages. That is, by knowing foreign languages, we can work in many places. For example, we can work as translators, guides for many foreign guests, teach various modern educational courses, provide guest services in various locations, and work in information technology and other locations. It is impossible to imagine today's increasingly globalized world without foreign languages. As we mentioned, knowing a foreign language is necessary and necessary for every

field. Currently, various ways and methods of learning foreign languages are being created.

In other words, introducing children of kindergarten age with the help of various pictures, games and cartoons in a foreign language and raising children's interest in it is being carried out effectively. Today, the best way to learn a language is writing, listening, working with various texts and speaking methods. Knowing the following four methods is very important now. In order to know these at a high level, grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation should be good. Therefore, it is very difficult to learn a foreign language without knowing the following three things. Another way to facilitate language learning is to use ready-made speech patterns in a foreign language. These phrases will make it much easier for you to speak a foreign language.

At the same time, difficulties arise for teachers of foreign languages, who need to solve the problems of preserving the language and culture of the most global language and the worldview of another foreign language. The main conditions for effective interaction between representatives of different cultures are mutual understanding, mutual respect for each other and a tolerant attitude towards different cultures. In intercultural communication, the level of intercultural communication and the depth of understanding (basic English and deep penetration into the national culture) are important. According to the "mosaic theory", or "salad bowl theory", or "salad bowl theory" (salad bowl theory = ethnic stew theory = tossed salad theory), in a multinational society, individual cultures do not disappear, that is, they do not merge into a single culture, but retain their individuality, and at the same time there is a common national flavor" [3]. At the current stage of society's development, the process of intercultural communication is taking on new forms. The development of electronic means of communication has led to the development of "computer-mediated forms of communication, which have radically changed the nature of discourse." The idea of a global village is increasingly being expressed: "The world, entangled in electronic networks, is turning into a "global village" where space and time are abolished, and the life of each individual flies by "at the speed of light"" [4]. In the process of interaction between participants in intercultural communication, various electronic means of communication are widely used: e-mail, Skype, voice and video communication, social services Facebook, Twitter, as well as platforms for creating your own blogs and much more. Thus, teaching foreign languages in the era of globalization has its own characteristics and problems. One of the problems of teaching English for many countries is the choice of teaching content, that is, the choice of the volume of educational material sufficient for communication, in other words - "what to teach", which version of the English language and which culture to teach? Is this not a question of the tendency to simplify the educational material in the content of textbooks?

Another problem of teaching foreign language in the era of globalization is the methodological side, namely how to teach and with what means. Innovations in teaching foreign languages in the era of globalization are associated with changes in the content of teaching foreign languages, changes in pedagogical technologies, methods and means of teaching. According to A. Yu. Uvarov, traditional education is being transformed and acquiring new forms: "It can be assumed that as revolutionary changes in the field of telecommunications and cloud technologies increase, we will move towards "education in the cloud" at different levels during the transformation of traditional education: school/university, educational cluster of the city, region, country and the world" [5]. Thus, the main difficulties of modern language education are in the content of teaching, methods and means of teaching. These categories of methods of teaching foreign languages in the innovative process of social life are also being transformed, as is the entire education system.

I.L. Bim believes that the components of the content of teaching foreign languages are the objectives of teaching, that is, foreign language communicative competence and its components (linguistic, speech, socio-cultural, compensatory and educational-cognitive

competences), the activities of the teacher and students, as well as feelings and emotions caused by the interaction of the identified components of the content of teaching, which contribute to the creation of a favorable learning environment. I.L. Bim, like other methodologists, considers the text as the main unit of the content of teaching. The text acts in teaching as an object for recognition visually (reading) and by ear (listening), as well as as a product of speech production (speaking, writing). The text is capable of carrying any information from all areas of knowledge, which gives a diverse focus to teaching foreign languages. Teaching reading (working with text) is directly related to teaching speaking. Also L.V. Shcherba paid special attention to reading in his works: "Teachers who believe that one can learn to read only to the extent of one's proficiency in spoken language, unwittingly find themselves in a false circle: in order to learn to read books, one must learn to speak, but it turns out that in order to learn to speak, one must read a lot" [2].

Thus, according to the definition of I.L. Bim, the main components of the content of training are the objectives of training, the activities of the participants in the educational process and a favorable learning environment, which largely depends on the conditions in which the educational process is carried out, that is, we are talking about a modern information and educational environment. Considering the text (information) as the main unit of content in teaching foreign languages, using the capabilities of the Internet, we have access to relevant, authentic information in Internet resources, which helps to increase the motivation of students to study foreign languages. Information about the latest events in the world (sports, culture, politics, etc.), texts of native speakers (speeches of politicians at conferences, seminars, information from TV presenters, films, videos, etc.) expand the content of the textbook, which arouses interest in another language and another culture. The richest information resources of the Internet, when used skillfully, have a positive effect on the process of acquiring knowledge. Studying a foreign language and foreign culture in comparison with the native language and native culture is one of the characteristics of modern language education. Therefore, teachers of foreign languages need to create situations for online interaction of students with native speakers. Real and virtual travel contributes to a deeper study of a foreign language, foreign culture and knowledge of one's own culture. Today, the virtual space provides a wide range of online educational communities for students and schoolchildren: the European school network www.eun.org, the social network of education workers <http://www.nsportal.ru>, the In-fourok project <https://infourok.ru/>, digital education <http://www.digital-edu.ru/>, open class <http://www.openclass.ru/og>, the forum of English teachers <http://www.englishteachers.ru>, etc.

Information from the websites of the capitals of the world, international organizations, virtual museums, electronic libraries, electronic newspapers and magazines, etc. (the electronic newspaper The Times <http://www.thetimes.co.uk/tto/news/>, the website of the British Councils <http://www.britishcouncil.org>, the encyclopedia Britannica <http://www.britannica.com>, etc.) is available to every participant in the educational process and contributes to the formation of socio-cultural competence in students. Answering today's questions of "how to teach" and "by what means" to teach a foreign language, one cannot ignore modern information and communication technologies and the possibilities of Web 2.0 (Skype, video conferences, chats, forums, electronic libraries, virtual museums, virtual worlds, etc.). Provided that the students' activities are methodically justified, they allow increasing the volume of speech acts and the density of communication in a foreign language. The density of speech practice in a foreign language can also be increased by mobile learning, which is currently developing in the form of the BYOD (Bring Your Own Device) concept and "just in time" technologies. Today, it has become common for people to communicate using different types of digital devices (mobile phones, smartphones, iPhones, tablet computers, etc.). And in education, traditional teaching aids are used in combination with digital tools, as a

supplement. However, they have great potential for achieving educational results; it is only necessary to correctly correlate their capabilities, educational goals, and the organization of educational activities.

The process of modernization of the education system places high demands on the teacher. He must have a high level of not only subject knowledge and skills, but also pedagogical, information and communication technologies, as well as technologies in the field of distance learning of foreign languages. Teaching foreign languages in the era of globalization has its own characteristics and difficulties. Preparation for real intercultural communication determines the main goal of teaching foreign languages. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, a foreign language lesson is a crossroads of cultures, it is a fact of presenting a foreign language culture, it is a practice of intercultural communication, because each foreign word reflects a foreign world and a foreign culture [3]. One of the components of the goal of teaching foreign languages is socio-cultural competence, the formation of which directly depends on the formation of linguistic and speech competencies. Studying a language, we study the culture of native speakers. The emergence of a single global language, as S.G. Ter-Minasova, attracts the opportunity to solve many problems of international communication, reduce the huge financial costs of international organizations for translators, promote the exchange of information and, consequently, accelerate and improve scientific and technological progress, trade, business, etc. However, "the prospect of global unification of mankind, the interaction and interdependence of all people and all countries living peacefully and amicably in one global village, caused the opposite reaction, namely, forced all peoples to remember their languages and cultures, national traditions, tastes, values, which led to the awareness of the importance of preserving national identity" [4].

Teaching foreign languages is directly related to the innovative processes taking place in the world, in society. Modern communication technologies are being developed, the main mission of which is to optimize interaction and mutual understanding in human society. Today, a new approach to teaching foreign languages is needed. The formation of foreign language communicative competence of the younger generation, the education of morality, respectful attitude towards other cultures, successful communication and mutual understanding between peoples depend on the professional competence of school teachers and university lecturers and their mastery.

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